

KNOWLEDGE
WITHOUT
BOUNDARIES

EIFL 2021
ANNUAL
REPORT

WHERE WE WORK

In 2021, EIFL worked in partnership with library consortia in 38 countries and ran projects in an additional 15 countries where we do not have library consortia.

- **PARTNER COUNTRIES** are countries where we have a formal agreement with the national library consortium. EIFL partner consortia work with all EIFL programmes.
- **PROJECT COUNTRIES** are countries in which we work with libraries on specific projects.

WHERE WE WORK

EIFL works in collaboration with libraries in 53 developing and transition countries.

AFRICA Botswana, Democratic Republic of Congo, Ethiopia, Ghana, Ivory Coast, Kenya, Lesotho, Malawi, Namibia, Senegal, South Africa, Tanzania, Uganda, Zambia, Zimbabwe **ASIA PACIFIC** Cambodia, China, Fiji, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Laos, Maldives, Mongolia, Myanmar, Nepal, Thailand, Uzbekistan **EUROPE** Armenia, Azerbaijan, Belarus, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Bulgaria, Croatia, Czech Republic, Estonia, Georgia, Hungary, Kosovo, Latvia, Lithuania, Moldova, North Macedonia, Poland, Romania, Serbia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Ukraine **LATIN AMERICA** Chile, Colombia **MIDDLE EAST & NORTH AFRICA** Palestine, Sudan, Syria.

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**OUR VISION IS A WORLD IN
WHICH ALL PEOPLE HAVE THE
KNOWLEDGE THEY NEED TO
ACHIEVE THEIR FULL POTENTIAL.**

Photo by Augustinas Žukovas

WHO WE ARE

EIFL (Electronic Information for Libraries) is an international not-for-profit organization that works with libraries in developing and transition countries to enable access to knowledge for education, learning, research and sustainable community development.

Our strategy has three main goals:

To advance a fair and sustainable transition from paywalled to open access content

Major achievements in 2021 -

- By the end of 2021, 12 agreements with publishers were in place enabling authors from our partner countries to publish for free or at reduced prices in open access in 2,500 journals. 938 authors benefited from these agreements in 2021 and published 1055 articles in open access.
- In 2021, Estonia, Fiji, Ghana, Latvia, Lithuania, Moldova and Palestine signed up for the EIFL-negotiated Read & Publish agreement with Cambridge University Press. Researchers can access journals and also publish articles in open access without paying Article Processing Charges.
- We provided advice to institutions that were developing open access policies. Eight institutions (in Armenia, Moldova, Poland and Serbia) adopted policies mandating deposit of research output in open access repositories, and eight more open access policies (in Armenia, Ghana, Kenya and Lesotho) are under discussion by university administrations.

To support research, teaching and learning

Major achievements in 2021 -

- We helped libraries to provide remote access to licensed e-resources by negotiating with technology service providers. In 2021, 169 libraries subscribed to EIFL-negotiated remote access services.
- We advocated for copyright reform to ensure the adoption of modern copyright laws that maximize access to content:
 - Participated in national copyright law review processes in Namibia, Nigeria, South Africa, Ukraine and Zimbabwe.
 - Contributed to ending the book famine for persons with print disabilities by supporting national implementation of the Marrakesh Treaty for persons with print disabilities in Belarus, Kenya, Namibia and Zimbabwe.
- Our advocacy work at the World Intellectual Property Organization (WIPO), where we advocate for exceptions and limitations for libraries in support of access to knowledge and the right to research, was strengthened by a grant from the Arcadia Fund.
- We advocated for creation and maintenance of open public infrastructures that enable the publication and sharing of research in open access journals and open repositories:
 - Contributed to adoption of national open science policies, mandating open science practices, in Bulgaria, Slovenia and Slovakia, and draft policies that are now being discussed in six countries (Armenia, India, Latvia, Romania, Uganda and Ukraine).

To foster digital transformation of public library services

Major achievements in 2021 -

- We built digital literacy skills and advocated for improvements of ICT infrastructure in Uganda:
 - With partners, launched a training-of-trainers programme for 25 public and community libraries. By the end of 2021, over 1,100 women and youth had completed digital skills training, delivered by our trained librarians. This training programme attracted donations of 50 computers for 10 libraries from ABSA Bank.
 - Continued our relationship with the Uganda Communications Commission (UCC). In 2021, UCC provided 10 computers, multipurpose printers and accessories to five public and two community libraries.
- We advocated at the Internet Governance Forum for inclusion of public libraries in national ICT rollout plans.
- We selected three libraries (in Bangladesh, Kenya and Uganda) for the EIFL Public Library Innovation Award for supporting education recovery during the COVID-19 pandemic.

DIRECTOR'S REPORT

At the time of writing this report, the war in Ukraine was very much on our minds. We stand by the people of Ukraine as they fight to defend their country. Ukraine is a country we know and love, and it is heartbreaking to see the suffering of its people and the destruction of our partner universities and libraries.

2021 had positive developments with respect to access to knowledge.

It was good to see the adoption of the UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science by UNESCO member states in November. Our Open Access Programme Manager, Iryna Kuchma, served on the UNESCO Open Science Advisory Committee as an international expert. The Recommendation sets international standards for open science, and we expect that it will advance open science policy development in many more countries, increasing openness to scientific research and knowledge.

COP26 (26th UN Climate Change Conference of the Parties) in Glasgow led to a global agreement on tackling the climate crisis. During a COP26 fringe event, the CEO of Creative Commons publicly announced a global campaign led by Creative Commons, EIFL and SPARC to promote open access, open science and open data as effective enabling strategies to accelerate progress towards solving the climate crisis and preserving global biodiversity. You will hear more about our campaign in 2022.

In 2021, we launched and started implementing our 2021 – 2023 strategic plan. In this report, under Who We Are (page 5), we highlight the results of our work in 2021. We also mark the 10th Anniversary of the EIFL Public Library Innovation Awards, featuring a selection of winning library services that are improving people's lives.

Thank you to everyone, our partners and funders, our board members and staff, who help to bring us closer to achieving our vision of a world in which all people have the knowledge they need to achieve their full potential.

RIMA KUPRYTE, DIRECTOR OF EIFL

Photo by Augustinas Žukovas

Public Library
Innovation
Award

PUBLIC LIBRARIES IMPROVING PEOPLE'S LIVES

Celebrating 10 years of the EIFL Public Library
Innovation Award

"I'm glad we can find this kind of library service in our city. My family encouraged me to try the library's smartphone training. I was scared and hesitant, but now I'm very happy I did!"

– ZELJKO SALOMON, AGED 70, WHO JOINED A SMARTPHONE TRAINING SERVICE FOR SENIORS OFFERED BY PUBLIC LIBRARY 'FRAN GALOVIC' KOPRIVNICA IN CROATIA

Every year EIFL invites public and community libraries in developing and transition countries to apply for an EIFL Public Library Innovation Award. The calls highlight important community development issues and recognize innovative uses of digital technology in services that improve people's lives.

Since 2011 EIFL has completed 15 innovation award calls and announced the names of 53 winners in Africa, Asia, Europe, Latin America and the Caribbean. As we celebrate the 10th anniversary of the awards, we take pleasure in sharing with you a selection of the winners. Many of these libraries have encouraged governments to invest in public library connectivity and inspired other libraries to introduce similar services in their communities.

Public libraries contributing to community economic wellbeing

Kenya - Meru Public Library / Winner 2018

"Young people have the mentality that farming is for old people. They do not think farming is cool," says Richard Wanjohi, head of Meru Public Library. The library is changing young people's attitudes to farming, and opening up new avenues for income generation by training them to use ICT, teaching them business skills and then allowing them to work on a 100 square metre farm, which the library manages. "We start with quick growing crops — kale, capsicums and spinach — so our learners can see results," said Richard. The library also connects the young people to online information services for farmers. "I have been able to put my family land into good use to get better produce. That was made possible through the skills and ICT connection to farming," said one young farmer.

Philippines - Butuan City Library / Winner 2018

Every year, over two million Filipinos travel abroad to earn higher wages so that they can help support their families back home. "We call them our 'modern heroes' for helping our economy with their remittances," said Jessica Clarito, head of Butuan City Library. In partnership with the Philippine Overseas Employment Administration, the library's e-government support service and computer literacy training has helped over 10,000 people with online applications for Overseas Employment Certificates. "This is already my fourth year under a six-year contract as an Overseas Filipino Worker in Dubai. I used to go to Manila just to get my Certificate, but now it is much closer and the librarians will help you on what you need to do," said Shereen, who works as a Health Technician in Dubai.

Serbia - Belgrade City Library / Winner 2012

This library's financial literacy training is helping students, young adults, families and pensioners to manage their money wisely and save for the future. In addition to providing financial literacy training, the library established the 'Novcici' ('Coins') website, which gives practical advice about budgets, banks, credit and investments. The service is extremely popular. In the period 2010/12, 3,500 high school students attended financial literacy workshops in the library, and almost 100 people a day visited the website. "I visit my library's Novcici website every time I have a dilemma about my finances," said Doroteja Kovacevi, a successful saver.

Public libraries contributing to community health

Brazil - 'Argentina Lopes Tristão' library / Winner 2018

This library, in Domingos Martins, is changing the lives of vulnerable women suffering from depression through an ICT training programme, in which young people do the training. The course lasts 90 hours, covering Microsoft applications (Word, Excel and PowerPoint) and how to use the internet. "The basic computer course in the library has changed my life. I used to live without perspectives, in a vulnerable situation, and I never imagined that I could learn so many good things. Now I know I can. It is as if a new world arises. I have gone back to school and I will not stop studying," said Lucineia Helena Tavares.

Romania - 'Gh.Asachi' County Library Iași / Winner 2012

"From the bottom of my heart, I thank the library that taught me how to save somebody's life!" said Carmen Pasat, teacher at High School 'Miron Costin'. 'Gh.Asachi' County Library in Iași trains librarians in a network of 86 public libraries across Romania in First Aid skills, and they in turn offer First Aid workshops in their communities. The library partners with the Red Cross, hospitals and the ambulance service. Health professionals and ambulance staff volunteer to give lectures and help manage an online training course provided through the library's website. In just over a year (2011/12) the library trained over 90 librarians in the network, who trained over 2,000 people in vital First Aid skills.

Uganda - Hoima Public Library / Winner 2012

The number of library users seeking health information more than doubled after Hoima Public Library introduced its health service

in 2010, according to an impact assessment survey conducted in 2012. The survey also found that 20% more mothers who use the library now have mosquito nets in their homes, and sleep under them regularly. The service provides free access to the internet in an e-health corner, and, from 2010 – 2012, working with the Red Cross, NGO's and local hospitals, trained over 400 health workers, 2,000 students and 700 members of the general public to use the internet to access reliable health information. "The library's ICT health corner guides our patients and also provides access to programmes like Skype, Twitter, Facebook and email, which are all very important in service delivery," said Brian Maccoine, clinical officer, Hoima Regional Referral Hospital.

Public libraries contributing to social inclusion

Croatia - Public Library 'Fran Galovic' Koprivnica / Winner 2012 and 2018

The library is breaking down social barriers and stigma between Roma and Croat communities through activities, including ICT training, that bring children and youth from the two communities together in the library. The activities increased library membership from Roma communities and drew praise from the (then) Deputy Mayor of Koprivnica, Vesna Želježnjak, who said: "The library's training programme is a significant contribution towards integration of the Roma population." In 2018 the library introduced another service to promote social inclusion — helping seniors to use their smartphones to improve their quality of life. Three high school students volunteered to conduct training and provide individual consultations for learners. "My family says I'm smarter now!" said 70-year-old Nada Dombai, a newly-skilled smartphone user.

Kazakhstan - 'Oralkhan Bokeev' City Library of Ust-Kamenogorsk / Winner 2019

By teaching digital skills to young people living with disabilities the library is helping them to become more active, confident and independent. The majority of the library's trainees are people with neuro-psychological disability and cerebral palsy. Librarians develop training programmes focused on the personal needs and interests of each learner. Two young motorcycle enthusiasts inspired fellow trainees to take an interest in researching the internet to learn more about different brands and models, the history and production of motorcycles and legal issues related to vehicle ownership. "Now I understand different brands and even made a short online video about my favourite bike models," said Sasha Gerasimov.

Uganda - Kitungesa Community Library / Winner 2012

This library, which serves rural communities in Masaka District, is playing a vital role in ending the isolation of deaf children, who for the first time are sharing space with hearing children in the library, taking part in lessons in computer use and English language, playing games and using Skype to communicate with friends in Canada. The library also established a Ugandan sign language club, in which deaf students teach sign language to hearing children. "Through the library, deaf students learn from other community members by interacting with them," said Lydia, who is one of 100 students from the Good Samaritan School for the Deaf.

Public libraries responding to COVID-19

Kenya - Nakuru Public Library / Winner 2021

When Kenyan schools closed due to COVID-19 in March 2020, Government guidance was to move teaching online. However, most teachers in public (state-run) schools had not yet integrated computers into their classes, and lacked digital skills. The library decided to address this situation by raising teachers' awareness about free online teaching and learning tools, like Zoom, Microsoft Teams, Google Classroom and

Moodle, and training teachers to use these tools. By the time lockdown restrictions were lifted just under a year later, the library had trained 30 teachers at 10 schools: "I am now able to use the internet to transmit knowledge to students. My students can confidently access e-resources and submit assignments online," said Doreen Nyamosi, a teacher at Nakuru Central Secondary School.

Peru - Main Public Library of Lima / Winner 2020

"This is a blessing for me since the pandemic is there, and I cannot go to the library." When the country went into lockdown, the library moved services online. However, librarians were worried about people who did not have access to the internet, and might be isolated and lonely. They came up with the idea of a telephone reading service — 'Aló BNP'. In just a few months, over 200 people registered — the majority (60%) were seniors — the oldest aged 95, the youngest five. Clients provided information about their age, gender, topics of interest and reading preferences, for example, books, newspapers or magazines, poetry, fiction or nonfiction. The library assigned each new client a reader, who then telephoned the client for reading sessions at agreed times.

Ukraine - 'A. Gaidar' Central City Children's Library Melitopol / Winner 2020

To help families cope with stress and keep children busy and creative during the national lockdown, the library moved its popular free School of Drawing online — but with a difference: instead of professional art teachers, the children became the teachers. Within a couple of months, the Video School of Drawing, on the library's Facebook page, had become the most popular library activity in the city of Melitopol. Ten young teachers recorded dozens of classes, teaching different painting styles and techniques: abstract, landscape, animation, 3D. The youngest teacher was aged seven, and the most experienced was 14. The classes attracted hundreds of positive comments: "I love watercolour, I thought it was really difficult to work with, but Anastasia is such a clear teacher," wrote Polina.

Public libraries contributing to education

Cameroon - 'Cercle de lecture et d'animation culturelle' (CLAC) / Winner 2016

CLAC's mobile library — known as 'Street CLAC' — takes laptop and tablet computers and books to schools in poor neighbourhoods of Yaoundé and offers children free online maths and computer coding classes. The fun online maths classes, developed by the library's NGO partner, Khan Academy, include video tutorials and exercises. In coding classes, the children learn how to programme animations and create interactive stories and videos. The service was launched in 2016, and within a few months it was reaching over 1,500 children in seven schools. After school hours, the mobile library travels across the city and stops at locations like markets, and offers free ICT, job-seeking and entrepreneurship training.

Colombia - Biblioteca Oasis del Saber, Bogotá / Winner 2015

"Before, at the market, I had to ask people to help me to read the names of the products. Now I'm proud to do it for myself," said Ana Cecilia Vera Pava. Ana is a graduate of the library's literacy and numeracy course, titled 'Growing Adults', in which learners aged from 14 to 80 learn together. The course includes lessons, online games, quizzes, listening to audiobooks and the radio, and watching animated films. All learners must complete the full course, attending 12 hours of classes per week, for 10 months. At the end of the course, learners achieve the same level of literacy and numeracy as grade three primary school students.

Lithuania - Kaunas Municipal 'Vincas Kudirka' Public Library / Winner 2016 and 2020

The library's ICT training initiative is encouraging young people to take up careers in digital technology and technical engineering. Training takes place in the library's 'Future Laboratory 3D', a space where learners can find equipment like 3D printers, robotics kits and software for computer-aided design, engineering and coding. They are free to experiment and get practical experience while working on simple and complex projects.

Training is supported by careers guidance, site visits to technology companies and work experience internships. "I know that my future will be in engineering and programming. Activities in the library's laboratory have opened up a whole new world of possibilities for the future," said Marius Kibilda, student, aged 19. At the height of the COVID-19 pandemic, the library's 3D printers worked day and night to print hands-free door openers to prevent infection and vital protective equipment for medics. EIFL awarded the library an Innovation Award for Responding to COVID-19 in 2020.

The EIFL Public Library Innovation Awards in numbers

10
years

15
calls for
applications

53
winners

24
countries

4
continents

Thank you to the Bill and Melinda Gates Foundation Global Libraries Programme for supporting the EIFL Public Library Innovation Awards. Thanks also to the evaluators who reviewed applications and helped us to identify the winners.

MEET THE PEOPLE

Using knowledge to change their lives
and the lives of others

JOSEPH M. KAVULYA

**PROFESSOR, UNIVERSITY LIBRARIAN,
CHUKA UNIVERSITY
KENYA**

Professor Joseph Kavulya is chairperson of EIFL's partner consortium in Kenya, the Kenya Library and Information Services Consortium (KLISC), and has been involved in national and international copyright reform.

In 2019, he was one of five African librarians supported by EIFL to take part in negotiations at the WIPO (World Intellectual Property Organization) meeting in Geneva on copyright limitations and exceptions for libraries, archives and museums.

"I was proud to be one of those voicing the concerns of African nations at the WIPO meeting," says Joseph.

"In Kenya, copyright law is restrictive and not very clear. As a result, librarians are fearful of copying case studies, tables or even excerpts from texts. They decline to copy even a few pages for users to avoid the risk of litigation. They are afraid of breaking the law."

EIFL has played an important role in facilitating the relationship between KLISC and KECOBO (the Kenya Copyright Board), he says. In 2020, EIFL and KLISC submitted joint comments to KECOBO on Kenya's draft Intellectual Property Bill 2020. "In the draft bill, there was no prior input from librarians. Through our comments, KECOBO is now more aware of the importance of limitations and exceptions for libraries and educational institutions, and has committed to reviewing the bill," says Joseph.

In 2021, EIFL, KLISC and KECOBO worked together to plan a series of webinars for various stakeholders in Kenya on copyright exceptions and other key topics that will continue in 2022. "We expect that these webinars that include local and international experts will raise awareness and support our case while the law is being reviewed."

"My dream is that the revised Intellectual Property Bill will address library concerns about supporting research, teaching and learning in Kenya."

– PROF JOSEPH KAVULYA

PHIONAH AGABA

ENTREPRENEUR UGANDA

During the COVID-19 lockdown, Pheona Agaba, of Mbarara City, was keen to keep busy and to help other women earn desperately needed income. She was in contact with a small group of widows, single mothers and girls who were struggling to make a living selling crafts.

She began using her smartphone to research the internet for ideas to help the group to increase their earnings. But browsing was expensive. She quickly ran out of data and could not afford to top-up.

“We heard about the free internet and training at Mbarara City Library, so we went to investigate. It was perfect — but most of our group had never used a computer before,” says Phionah.

The librarian, who had completed a training-of-trainers programme organized by EIFL, Maendeleo Foundation and the National Library of Uganda, offered to teach members of the group to use computers and the internet.

“We became regular visitors to the library, learning to use computers properly, and researching YouTube for new craft skills — how to make kilims, to dye mats, to make mirrors and Christmas decorations.

“Just before Christmas, we rented a shop to sell our products as gifts. The librarian taught us about digital marketing, using social media, and we also started selling our produce online.

“Now we are doing outreach work to teach craft skills to women in other communities. And next year we will start our own learning channel on YouTube to share skills videos in Ugandan languages,” says Phionah.

Photo by Mwesigwa Allan

“We are happy with the income we are earning. We could not have succeeded without the help of the library and the skills we learnt there.”

– PHIONAH AGABA

OLEKSANDR BEREZKO

ASSOCIATE PROFESSOR, LVIV
POLYTECHNIC NATIONAL
UNIVERSITY
UKRAINE

In November 2021, Ukraine launched a draft National Plan for Open Science. The plan was the culmination of six months of intensive meetings organized by the Ministerial Working Group on Development of the Ukrainian National Plan for Open Science.

Oleksandr Berezko coordinates the Working Group, which comprises experts from 18 Higher Education Institutions, research institutes, libraries, and NGOs — including EIFL.

Ukraine was one of the first countries where EIFL began promoting open access, with an awareness raising workshop in 2004.

Over the years EIFL has, through a variety of strategies and activities, helped to build open access and open science capacity of scholars, research managers and librarians. Today, Ukraine has over 160 open access institutional repositories and 17 institutions have adopted open access policies.

“EIFL’s long and consistent involvement helped lay the ground and smooth the passage of the draft National Plan,” said Oleksandr.

Once formalized, the National Plan will mandate open access to research output and create conditions for effective work with Open / FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) data. The draft Plan is currently being reviewed by government ministries, and discussed at a series of public events.

“The plan will help integrate our research infrastructures into European e-infrastructures — the EOSC (European Open Science Cloud). And it will reform research assessment, promote citizen science, and build capacity in open science,” said Oleksandr.

“Open Science is science done right. It is a unique opportunity for Ukrainian research to become fully integrated into the European and global systems and finally leave all the post-Soviet rudiments behind. Implementation of Open Science in Ukraine will be one of the urgent tasks after the victory over Russia.”

– OLEKSANDR BEREZKO

AUŠRA VAŠKEVIČIENĖ

ADMINISTRATOR, LITHUANIAN RESEARCH LIBRARY CONSORTIUM LITHUANIA

The Lithuanian Research Library Consortium (LMBA), EIFL's partner consortium, has 46 member institutions. Aušra Vaškevičienė, EIFL Licensing Coordinator in Lithuania, is part of the LMBA team that conducts annual negotiations with publishers for licensed access to scholarly e-resources for LMBA members. LMBA also joins agreements negotiated by EIFL.

In 2021, LMBA member libraries subscribed to 78 scholarly journals, databases and e-book collections, including five negotiated by EIFL. The e-resources are very well used: in 2021 more than 3.2 million journal articles and more than 538,000 e-book chapters were downloaded.

"We use the EIFL model licence as the basis for our negotiations with publishers. We also learned from EIFL on how to negotiate Read & Publish agreements and we apply EIFL's negotiating principles," says Aušra.

In 2021, the LMBA signed two Read & Publish agreements, which combine reading access with free publishing in open access for authors. "We were encouraged that authors used all 17 vouchers for publishing in open access in the American Chemical Society journals. For 2022, we will have Read & Publish agreements with two more publishers, bringing our total to four.

"We also promote to researchers the agreements that EIFL negotiates for waived or discounted Article Processing Charges. In 2021, 29 articles were published in open access in journals of three publishers," says Aušra.

"LMBA has partnered with EIFL for over 20 years, since 1999. We benefited from big discounts negotiated by EIFL for 30 e-resources, and the starting prices ensure that we continue to pay affordable prices for these products."

– AUŠRA VAŠKEVIČIENĖ

OUR NETWORK

EIFL partner library consortia nominate coordinators who serve as the main point of contact between EIFL's Programmes and their consortium. In their countries, they lead and facilitate activities initiated by EIFL, and have been central to our success and achievements over the years.

We would like to thank all our Country Coordinators, Licensing Coordinators, Open Access Coordinators and Copyright Coordinators for their enthusiasm and hard work in 2021.

ALBANIA

Consortium of Albanian Libraries

Country Coordinator: Albana Velianj
Licensing Coordinators: Renata Bardhi and Mirlona Buzo
Open Access Coordinator: Renata Bardhi (from February)

ARMENIA

Digital Library Association of Armenia (DLAA)

Country Coordinator: Anna Chulyan
Licensing Coordinator: Tatevik Tamazyan (from April)
Copyright Coordinator: Hasmik Galstyan
Open Access Coordinator: Tigran Zakaryan

AZERBAIJAN

Azerbaijan Library and Information Consortium for Availability of Electronic Information (AzLIC)

Country Coordinator: Jamila Yusifova and Ilfat Ibrahimov (from April)
Licensing Coordinator: Ilfat Ibrahimov (from April)

BELARUS

Council of Belarusian Libraries on Information Cooperation (BelCoLib)

Country & Open Access Coordinator: Viatcheslav Britchkovski
Copyright Coordinator: Viktor Pshibytko
Licensing Coordinator: Mariya Domovskaja

BOTSWANA

Botswana Libraries Consortium (BLC)

Country & Licensing Coordinator: Naniki Maphakwane
Copyright Coordinator: Khutsafalo Kadimo
Open Access Coordinator: Bobana Badisang (until March); Poloko Ntokwane (from March)

CHINA

Library Network of the Chinese Academy of Sciences

Country Coordinator: Xiwen Liu
Open Access & Copyright Coordinator: Kunhua Zhao

CONGO

Consortium des Bibliothèques Académiques du Congo (COBAC)

Country Coordinator: Eliezer Mwongane
Licensing Coordinator: Jean Baptiste Unen

ESTONIA

Consortium of Estonian Libraries Network (ELNET)

Country & Licensing Coordinator: Marika Meltsas
Copyright Coordinator: Karmen Linask
Open Access Coordinator: Elena Sipria-Mironov

ETHIOPIA

Consortium of Ethiopian Academic and Research Libraries (CEARL)

Country Coordinator: Derib Erget Mamuye
Copyright Coordinator: Ato Yoseph Bizuneh
Licensing Coordinators: Bedassa Motuma Beyene and Derib Erget Mamuye
Open Access Coordinator: Solomon Mekonnen Tekle (until March); Getnet Lemma (from March)

FIJI

Fiji Library Consortium

Country & Licensing Coordinator: Udyia Shukla

GEORGIA

Georgian Integrated Library Information System Consortium (GILISC) 2017

Country, Open Access & Copyright Coordinator: Nino Pavliashvili (from April)
Licensing Coordinator: Marika Zhorzholiani

GHANA

Consortium of Academic and Research Libraries in Ghana (CARLIGH)

Country Coordinator: Richard Bruce Lamptey
Copyright Coordinator: Teresa Adu
Licensing Coordinator: Mac Anthony Cobblah
Open Access Coordinator: Donyina Fokuo and Nana Tuhufu Quagraine

IVORY COAST

Consortium des Bibliothèques de l'Enseignement Supérieur de Cote d'Ivoire (COBES-CI)

Country & Licensing Coordinator: Cécile Coulibaly
Copyright Coordinator: Ahou Marie-Claire Allou
Open Access Coordinator: Adjoh Hortense Kakpo epse Outtara

KENYA

Kenya Libraries and Information Services Consortium (KLISC)

Country & Licensing Coordinator: Arnold Mwanzu
Copyright Coordinator: Janegrace Kinyanjui
Open Access Coordinator: George Njoroge

KOSOVO

Consortium of Electronic Libraries in Kosovo (CELC)

Country, Licensing & Open Access Coordinator: Bukurije Haliti

KYRGYZSTAN

Kyrgyzstan Library Information Consortium (KLIC)

Country Coordinator: Jyldyz Bekbalaeva
Copyright & Open Access Coordinator: Safia Rafikova (until October); Tolgonai Kozhokanova (from October)
Licensing Coordinator: Iryna Pak (until October); Tolgonai Kozhokanova (from October)

LAOS

Laos Library and Information Consortium (LALIC)

Country, Copyright & Licensing Coordinator: Sypha Phongsavath
Open Access Coordinator: Sisavanh Linsavath

LATVIA

Culture Information Systems Centre

Country, Licensing & Open Access
Coordinator: Agrita Sagalajeva
Copyright Coordinator: Inta Mikluna

LESOTHO

Lesotho Library Consortium (LELICO)

Country Coordinator: Buhle Mbambo-Thata
Copyright Coordinator: Pontso Mkuebe
Licensing Coordinator: Tahleho Tseole
Open Access Coordinator: Matseliso Kabeli

LITHUANIA

Lithuanian Research Library Consortium (LMBA)

Country & Licensing Coordinator: Ausra Vaskeviciene
Copyright Coordinator: Janina Marcinkeviciene
Open Access Coordinator: Gintare Tautkeviciene

MALAWI

Malawi Library and Information Consortium (MALICO)

Country & Licensing Coordinator: Geoffrey Francis Salanje (until September)
Licensing Coordinator: Trevor Namondwe (from December)
Open Access Coordinator: Fiskani Ngwira

MALDIVES

(No name – under development)

Country & Licensing Coordinator: Aminath Shiuna

MOLDOVA

Electronic Resources for Moldova (REM)

Country & Licensing Coordinator: Elena Tudor Railean
Copyright Coordinator: Mariana Harjevschi
Open Access Coordinator: Natalia Cheradi

NAMIBIA

Namibia Library Consortium (NALICO)

Country & Copyright Coordinator: Victoria Isaacks
Licensing Coordinator: Namutenya Hamwaalwa

NEPAL

Nepal Library and Information Consortium (NeLIC)

Country, Licensing & Open Access
Coordinator: Jagadish Aryal

NORTH MACEDONIA

Macedonian e-Libraries (MEL)

Country, Licensing & Copyright Coordinator:
Miodrag Dadasovic

PALESTINE

Palestinian Library and Information Consortium (PALICO)

Country Coordinators: Diana Sayej Naser;
Rami Alhindawi for Gaza
Licensing Coordinator: Diana Sayej Naser
(until September); Mohammad Abu
Hamdieh (from September)
Open Access Coordinator: Mohammad Abu
Hamdieh (until September); Asad Tom (from
September)

SENEGAL

Consortium des Bibliothèques de l'Enseignement Supérieur du Sénégal (COBESS)

Country & Licensing Coordinator:
Youssofpha Gueye
Copyright Coordinator: Awa Diouf Cisse
Open Access Coordinator: Mandiaye Ndiaye

SERBIA

Serbian Library Consortium for Coordinated Acquisition (KoBSON)

Country Coordinator: Tatjana Timotijevic
Licensing Coordinators: Tatjana Timotijevic
and Boris Denadic
Copyright Coordinator: Dragana Milunovic
Open Access Coordinator: Milica Sevkusic

SLOVENIA

Consortium of Slovene Electronic Collections (COSEC)

Country Coordinator: Karmen Stular Sotosek
Licensing Coordinator: Herman Erculj
Open Access Coordinator: Alenka Kavcic-Colic

SUDAN

Sudanese Academic Libraries Consortium (SALC)

Country Coordinator: Iman Abdelrahman
Copyright & Licensing Coordinator:
Abdelaziz Gabir
Open Access Coordinator: Rania M. Hassan
Baleela

TANZANIA

Consortium of Tanzania Universities and Research Libraries (COTUL)

Country & Open Access Coordinator: Paul
Samwel Muneja
Licensing Coordinator: Cyril Ndekakao

THAILAND

Electronic Information for Libraries in Thailand (eifl-Thailand)

Country, Copyright and Licensing
Coordinator: Soeythip Sukul
Open Access Coordinator: Adisak Sukul

UGANDA

Consortium of Uganda University Libraries (CUUL)

Country Coordinator: David Bukenya
Copyright Coordinator: Eric Haumba
Licensing Coordinator: Thecla Atukwase
(until June); Drake Tamale (from June)
Open Access Coordinator: Hassan
Ssengooba

UKRAINE

Association 'Informatio-Consortium'

Country, Copyright, Licensing & Open Access
Coordinator: Oleksii Vasyliev

UZBEKISTAN

EIFL Uzbekistan Consortium

Country Coordinator: Gulrukh Iskandarova
Licensing Coordinator: Alisher Kattavekov
Open Access Coordinator: Maksim
Savochkin

ZAMBIA

Zambia Library Consortium (ZALICO)

Country & Licensing Coordinator: Eness
Chitumbo
Copyright Coordinator: Benson Njobvu
Open Access Coordinator: Pilate Chewe

ZIMBABWE

Zimbabwe University Libraries Consortium (ZULC)

Country & Licensing Coordinator: Sarlomie
Zinyemba
Open Access Coordinator: Plaxedes
Chaitezvi
Copyright Coordinator: Rosemary Maturure
(from February)

OUR TEAM

Meeting of the EIFL network during the General Assembly that was held virtually from 20 – 21 October 2021.

STAFF

- Andrius Kriščiūnas**, Finance Manager
- Dick Kawooya**, Coordinator of Copyright Advocacy in Africa, Right to Research Project
- Edvaldas Baltrūnas**, Public Library Innovation Programme Coordinator
- Iryna Kuchma**, Open Access Programme Manager
- Jean Fairbairn**, Communications Manager, Website and Publications
- Jevgenija Ševcova**, Programmes and Events Coordinator

- Louise Stoddard**, Communications Manager
- Ramunė Petuchovaitė**, Public Library Innovation Programme Manager
- Rima Kuprytė**, Director
- Romy Beard**, Licensing Programme Manager
- Susan Schnuer**, Public Library Innovation Programme Capacity Building Manager
- Teresa Hackett**, Copyright and Libraries Programme Manager
- Ugnė Lipeikaitė**, Public Library Innovation Programme Impact Manager

MANAGEMENT BOARD

- Arnold Hirshon**, Chairperson, Kelvin Smith Library, Case Western Reserve University, USA (until September)
- Emilija Banionytė**, Chairperson, Vilnius County Adomas Mickevičius Public Library, Lithuania (from September)
- Colleen Campbell**, Max Planck Digital Library, Max Planck Society, Germany (from September)
- Adam Hyde**, Founder of Coko, Book Sprints, Paged.js, Open Publishing Awards and the Open Publishing Fest

- Jyldyz Bekbalaeva**, American University of Central Asia, Kyrgyzstan
- Joel Sam**, African Library and Information Associations and Institutions (AfLIA), Ghana

FINANCIAL REPORT

EIFL INCOME AND EXPENDITURE 2021

INCOME	€	%
• Programme income	2,512,233	69.6%
• Participation fees	432,362	12.0%
• General Support	603,063	16.7%
• Sponsorship, interest and other income	62,186	1.7%

Total 3,609,844

EXPENDITURE	€	%
• Programme delivery	538,836	80.8%
• Personnel & contracted expenses	105,309	15.8%
• Operating expenses	22,645	3.4%

Total 666,790

COMMITTED EXPENDITURE FOR 2022-2023 PROGRAMME DELIVERY 2,928,292

CONTINUITY RESERVE 392,485

OUR FUNDERS

We would like to thank the following organizations for their generous support for our work in 2021:

Organizations

- Arcadia Fund through American University, Washington College of Law
- Bill & Melinda Gates Foundation
- Embassy of Denmark, Myanmar
- European Commission Erasmus+ Programme through Lviv Polytechnic National University, Ukraine
- European Commission Horizon 2020 Programme
- Luxembourg Development Cooperation Agency (LuxDev)
- Open Society Foundations
- SPIDER, the Swedish Program for ICT in Developing Regions
- University of Luxembourg (UNILU)
- Wehubit Programme (implemented by the Belgian development agency, Enabel)

EVENTS

In 2021, EIFL organized, supported or took part in 149 events, workshops and conferences about issues that affect access to knowledge.

JANUARY

- FAIRIO project workshop on Findability of Research Information (Online)
- EIFL Power: Informal gathering, International Library and Information Group (ILIG) and UK library and information association (CILIP) (Online)
- Online Consultation for Indigenous People on the UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science
- Workshop series: Research Libraries, Researchers & the European Open Science Cloud (Online)
- DSpace 7 User-Facing Documentation Writing Sprint (Online)
- Webinar: EIFL Public Library Innovation Award Winners for the International Network of Library Innovators (INELI) India and South Asia members
- LTC2021 - International Conclave on eScience and Digital Libraries (Online)
- Occupy Library Innovators Hub project workshop: 'Libraries are great? Prove it! Data and evidence-based storytelling' (Online)

FEBRUARY

- Training librarians at the Faculty of Law and Political Science, National University of Laos, on use of e-resources (Online)
- Consultation on National University of Laos repository (Online)
- GRAPES project seminar: 'Managing and sharing research outputs: all you need to know' (Online)
- Webinar: Getting started with WIPO
- OpenAIRE virtual coffee break (Online)
- Webinar: RePol (Repository Policy Generator) & Shareyourpaper.org
- OPTIMA project kick-off meeting (Online)

MARCH

- Webinar: Open access publishing with OJS 3
- Webinar: Copyright policy action for open access
- Webinar: Dataverse software for research data repository
- Webinar: Open Science Communities
- Access Lab 2021 Conference (Online)
- Webinar: Enago product demo
- Press conference: Launch of statement in support of WTO TRIPS waiver proposal (Online)
- SPIDER Digital Impact and Networking Event (Online)
- Webinar: Introduction to EIFL Digital Research Literacy Training Programme Outline for Librarians

APRIL

- Webinar: Get into WIPO - Africa
- Webinar: Academic integrity
- Community call: Researcher engagement & researcher-friendly repository deposit workflows (Online)
- UKSG 44th Annual Conference (Online)
- National Open Research Forum (Ireland) webinar: Skills, incentives & rewards for Open Research
- Webinar: Choosing an effective publishing strategy
- Workshop: Building Consistency for Open Science in Europe - rhetorics and practises (Online)
- Workshop: Open Science in Turkey (Online)
- Research Data Alliance 17th Plenary Meeting (Online)
- Webinar: Open access publishing for Belarus authors
- Webinar: Institutional repository

- IFLA Copyright and Other Legal Matters Advisory Committee mid-term meeting (Online)
- IGF Dynamic Coalition on Public Access in Libraries: Agenda-setting meeting (Online)
- UNESCO Online Expert Meeting on Open Science and Intellectual Property Rights
- Workshop: Training of Trainers, Ugandan public librarians (Kampala, Uganda)
- Webinar to mark World IP Day: Libraries Mean Business
- Webinar: Using the open access route to increase research impact
- FAIRsFAIR and OpenAIRE projects workshop: 'National policy and support actions for research data skills - impact and experiences' (Online)
- International Perspectives Seminar: Guest lecture for Information Science students, Stuttgart Media University (Online)

MAY

- Webinar: Researcher identity & ORCID
- Intergovernmental special committee meeting of technical and legal experts to examine the Draft UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science (Online)
- Open Science & Research Data Management Train-the-Trainer Bootcamp (Online)
- Webinar: Managing and sharing research data
- Webinar: Open Science Action Plan, Ukraine
- A2K Coalition launch event (Online)
- Discussion with Open Book Publishers on the creation and usage of open access books (Online)
- 43rd Annual Meeting of the Society for Scholarly Publishing (Online)
- 4th AfLIA Conference & 6th African Library Summit (Online)

- Library Week in Kosovo (Pristina & online)
- Kenya Copyright Board webinar: The Publisher and Copyright (Online)
- RDA4EOSC webinar: Organizational approaches to enhancing skills and improving training (Online)
- LIBSENSE Community Call: ORCID - repository integrations (Online)
- Webinar: Writing a Data Management Plan
- Seminar: Open Science to leave no-one behind (Online)
- Webinar: The Lens open knowledge and discovery platform
- Mobile Digital Literacy Camp (Mukono, Uganda)
- Webinar: Shareyourpaper.org - repository setup

JUNE

- Next Library Festival 2021 (Online)
- Research Data Management and Open Access publishing training for PhD students at Akililu Lemma Institute of Pathobiology, Addis Ababa University (Addis Ababa, Ethiopia)
- 16th International Conference on Open Repositories (Online)
- Webinar: Preprints
- Webinar: Social media for research
- T-break for Public Library Trainers: Online training: successes and challenges (Online)
- Webinar: Introduction to Bibliometrics
- Webinar: Research Assessment: Equity, Diversity and Inclusion
- Third Ibero-American Conference for School and Public Libraries (Online)
- WIPO Copyright Committee (41st session) (Online)
- Webinar: Make your work count

- Open Access Policy Forum, Amref International University (Nairobi, Kenya, & Online)
- REPO webinar: Community Open Principles: Before, During and After the Global Pandemic

JULY

- Webinar: Open access publishing for Côte d'Ivoire
- Open Access Policy Forum, Alupe University College (Busia, Kenya, & Online)
- Open Access Policy Forum, University of Kabianga (Kericho, Kenya, & Online)
- University of Cape Coast scholarly communication stakeholders meeting (Cape Coast, Ghana, & Online)
- Research Data Management and Open Access publishing training for PhD students at Addis Ababa, Arba Minch and Debre Birhan universities (Addis Ababa, Arba Minch and Debre Birhan, Ethiopia)
- 2nd Open Science Conference: From tackling the pandemic to addressing climate change (Online)
- Open Access Policy Forum, Laikipia University, Kenya (Nyahururu, Kenya, & Online)
- T-break for Public Library Trainers: New public library services during the COVID-19 pandemic (Online)
- FORCE 11 Scholarly Communication Institute (FSCI) 2021 (Online)
- Consortium of Ugandan University Libraries (CUUL) Open Science Symposium (Online)
- Open Access Policy Forum, Chuka University (Chuka, Kenya, & Online)

AUGUST

- Webinar: Open access publishing for Ugandan authors
- Open Access and Research Data Management training for PhD students at Arsi University (Oromia, Ethiopia)
- IFLA World Library and Information Congress (Online)
- 14th Public Libraries' Meeting, Colombia (Online)
- Webinar: Open access publishing for Zambian authors

SEPTEMBER

- Nigeria Open Science Symposium (Online)
- OAI12 - Geneva Workshop on Innovations in Scholarly Communication (Online)
- T-break for Public Library Trainers: Library services for special groups (Online)
- Open Science Fair 2021 (Online)
- Open Access Scholarly Publishers Association Conference (OASPA) 2021 (Online)
- E-library training for Faculty of Law and Political Science, National University of Laos (Online)
- Burundi university libraries conference (Bujumbura, Burundi & Online)
- North Carolina Central University webinar: International Librarianship
- Mobile Digital Literacy Camp (Ajijja-Malongwe, Uganda)
- Online High-level Side Event of the 76th session of the UN General Assembly
- WTO Public Forum 2021 (Geneva, Switzerland)
- 15th Berlin Open Access Conference (Online)
- COAR Annual Meeting and General Assembly (Online)

OCTOBER

- WIPO Assemblies 2021 (Online)
- University of Illinois webinar: International Librarianship (Online)
- Webinar: EIFL-negotiated services for authors
- Annual Meeting of the Association of Lithuanian Municipal Public Libraries (Vilnius, Lithuania)
- T-break for Public Library Trainers: The power of advocacy (Online)
- Public Hearing on Nigeria's Copyright Bill 2021, Senate Committee on Trade and Investment (Abuja, Nigeria)
- International forum: Cycle of conversations on copyright and the international agenda, Mexico (Online)
- Community call: BOAI 20th Anniversary (Online)
- INELI webinar: Sharing innovations, ideas and inspirations (Online)

- Webinar: Scite product demo for researchers and librarians
- EIFL General Assembly (Online)
- National seminar on implementation of the Marrakesh Treaty, Belarus (Minsk, Belarus, & Online)
- Open Access Week 2021 (Online)
- COAR Asia Open Access 2021 Meeting (Online)
- Global Congress on Intellectual Property and the Public Interest (Online)

NOVEMBER

- Webinar: Licensing e-resources, the basics
- E-library training for Faculty of Law and Political Science, National University of Laos (Online)
- New Librarianship Symposia Series (Online)
- Webinar: Open Access and Books – Emerging New Models and the Global South
- Webinar: OpenAthens product demo
- ETD 2021 conference (Online)
- DSpace 7.1 user documentation sprint (Online)
- Europe, Middle East and Africa ICOLC meeting (Online)
- OPTIMA project workshops, Ukraine (Online)
- UKSG November Conference 2021 (Online)
- National conference: Copyright and Related Rights Draft Bill, Namibia (Windhoek, Namibia, & Online)
- Open Access Week: Experts panel, Busitema University, Uganda (Tororo, Uganda, & Online)
- Open Access Week Côte d'Ivoire (Abidjan, Côte d'Ivoire, & Online)
- EOSC Future Open Days (Online)
- Webinar for repository managers
- Panel discussion: Ukrainian National Plan for Open Science (Online)
- Webinar: Author workflow for open access publishing with SAGE

DECEMBER

- AfLIA webinar: Copyright governance: advocacy opportunities for librarians – national, regional, international

- e-Infrastructure Reflection Group Workshop under the Slovenian EU Presidency (Online)
- Webinar: Access to Reading Material for Visually Impaired Persons in Kenya
- T-break for Public Library Trainers: Impact of public library ICT services during the pandemic (Online)
- Internet Governance Forum (IGF) 2021 (Katowice, Poland)
- Knowledge exchange meeting: 'Libraries Helping Build a People-Centred Internet: Connectivity, Content and Competence' (Katowice, Poland)
- Coalition for Networked Information Fall Membership Meeting (Online)
- FORCE2021 Conference (Online)
- Mobile Digital Literacy Camp (Busesa, Uganda)
- E-AGE 21 Conference (Online)
- Consortium des Bibliothèques de l'Enseignement Supérieur du Sénégal (COBESS) General Assembly (Thiès, Senegal, & Online)
- Research & Innovation Day in Ukraine (Kyiv, Ukraine)

KEY

- Training, workshops and events organized and/or supported by EIFL
- Presentations given by EIFL staff or partners
- Conferences and events attended by EIFL staff

OUR PARTNERS

EIFL has built relationships with a wide range of organizations to make knowledge more accessible. In 2021, we worked with the following partners:

- African Library and Information Associations and Institutions (AfLIA)
- American University Washington College of Law (AUWCL)
- Arab Federation of Libraries and Information (AFLI)
- Arab States Research and Education Network (ASREN)
- ASEAN Public Libraries Information Network (APLiN)
- Association for Progressive Communicators (APC)
- Association of Lithuanian Municipal Public Libraries
- Bioline International
- Bookshare
- Centre for Internet and Society (India)
- Citizen's Services & Libraries, City of Aarhus, Denmark
- Coalition Publi.ca
- cOAlition S
- CODATA
- Coko Foundation
- COMMUNIA Association
- Confederation of Open Access Repositories (COAR)
- Copyright for Creativity
- Corporación Innovarte
- Coventry University
- Creative Commons
- Directory of Open Access Journals (DOAJ)
- DSpace Community Advisory Team (DCAT), DuraSpace
- Education International
- EOSC Association
- Fundación Karisma
- GÉANT
- Gigabit Library Network (GLN)
- Global Sustainability Coalition for Open Science Services (SCOSS)
- Google Scholar
- Fundación Karisma
- Harvard Open Access Project (HOAP)
- HIFA2020: Healthcare Information For All by 2020
- IEEE
- Information Power
- International Coalition of Library Consortia (ICOLC)
- International Council of Museums (ICOM)
- International Council on Archives (ICA)
- International Federation of Library Associations and Institutions (IFLA)
- International Network of Library Innovators (INELI) India and South Asia
- Internet Society
- Libraries Development, Local Government Management Agency Ireland
- Kenya National Library Service
- Knowledge Ecology International (KEI)
- Library Copyright Alliance (LCA)
- Maendeleo Foundation
- Namibia Library and Archives Service
- National Institute of Informatics of Japan
- National Library of Uganda
- Networked Digital Library of Theses and Dissertations (NDLTD)
- OpenAIRE AMKE
- Open Access Scholarly Publishers Association (OASPA)
- ORCID
- OA2020
- Peer 2 Peer University
- People Centered Internet (PCI)
- Progress Foundation
- Public Knowledge Project (PKP)
- Right to Research Coalition
- SPARC
- SPARC Europe
- Tactical Tech
- The International Relations Round Table (IRRT), American Library Association
- The Library and Information Association of Zambia (LIAZ)
- Ubiquity Press
- UbuntuNet Alliance
- UKSG
- UNESCO
- West and Central African Research and Education Network (WACREN)
- Wikimedia Deutschland
- World Intellectual Property Organization (WIPO)

KEY

- EIFL is a founding member/signatory
- EIFL is a member
- EIFL staff are board or committee members
- Official relations (including MoU)
- Working relationship

In addition, EIFL collaborated with 105 partners through European Commission-funded projects: European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) Future; Open Access Infrastructure for Research in Europe (OpenAIRE) Advance; Open Practices, Transparency and Integrity for Modern Academia (OPTIMA), and Strengthening Research Management and Open Science Capacities of HEIs in Moldova and Armenia (Minerva).

WHERE WE WORK

In 2021, EIFL worked in partnership with library consortia in 38 countries and ran projects in an additional 15 countries where we do not have library consortia.

- **PARTNER COUNTRIES** are countries where we have a formal agreement with the national library consortium. EIFL partner consortia work with all EIFL programmes.
- **PROJECT COUNTRIES** are countries in which we work with libraries on specific projects.

STAY CONNECTED

GET IN TOUCH

Mail: Mindaugo str. 23, LT-03214 Vilnius, Lithuania

Tel: +370 5 2080409 **Email:** info@eifl.net

For more information about EIFL and our work visit eifl.net